

BUSINESS
INCUBATION
CENTRE

Greece

YOUR SPACE BUSINESS JOURNEY
STARTS HERE

ESA UNCLASSIFIED

European Space Agency

UNDER THE LARGEST SPACE INNOVATION NETWORK IN THE WORLD

BUSINESS INCUBATION

25 Centres
>70 locations

200 new startups p/y

1200 startups selected

€ 200 M+ INVESTED

INNOVATION NETWORK

7 Technology Brokers

377 Technology Transfers

Access to ESA's Application Ambassadors

ESA SPACE SOLUTIONS ALLIANCE

Strategic partnerships

Supports startups, alumni and newcomers

Connecting current/ future decisionmakers

22nd ESA BIC, FOUNDED on 1st of MARCH 2021

ON THE MONTH THAT GREECE BECAME THE 16TH MEMBER OF ESA IN 2005 (16 YEARS AGO)

ESA BIC GREECE WAS ESTABLISHED TO...

- Strengthen the community of successful space-related startups in Greece under the ESA BIC scheme
- Underpin the growth and strengthening of the space cluster in Greece
- Contribute to the national strategies for space innovation
- Encourage further uptake of space-based services and support transfer of technologies from/to the space sector
- Create jobs and economic growth in the country

25 incubatees to be selected over the span of 5 years

WHO CAN APPLY?

- You have an innovative idea with space connection
- Your company is not older than five years or it is on the way to be established in Greece
- Your team members are residents with a working permit in Greece
- Majority-owned by founding entrepreneurs
- Viable business plan

SUPPORT PACKAGE FOR INCUBATEES

FINANCIAL SUPPORT

EUR 50,000 non-equity funding for product/service development and IPR

TECHNICAL, BUSINESS AND LEGAL SUPPORT

Up to 80 hours tech support, up to 50 hours of business development support, coaching and advise and up to 10 hours of legal and IPR advise by our Support Partners

REPUTATION

Reputation and branding of Incubator, including right of use of the ESA BIC brand, as a door opener to customers and investors

OFFICE SPACE

Access to office space at the Innovation Hub of Athens and to its Business Center, business support facilities and high-speed connectivity

COMMUNITY

Access to the international network of ESA Space Solutions, Corallia, si-Cluster members, ESA BIC support partners and ESA BICs in other Member States

TRAINING & INFRASTRUCTURE

Access to events, workshops and training, access to high-end infrastructure and equipment, access to software, data, platforms and other resources

ESA BIC Greece has received funding from the European Space Agency under ESA Contract No.4000133956/21

WITH WHOM?

BUSINESS
INCUBATION
CENTRE

Greece

OPERATIONAL & NETWORKING SUPPORT

FINANCIAL SUPPORT

TECHNICAL & BUSINESS SUPPORT

PROCESS

LOCTIO

CEO
Lazaros Kapsias

FOUNDED
2019

ORGANISATION TYPE
SME

PERSONNEL
Total: 12
Space: 12

TURNOVER (2021)
Total: 100,000 €
Space: 100,000 €

R&D INTERNAL
INVESTMENTS (2020)
500,000 €

CORE BUSINESS

Loctio is disrupting the positioning capabilities of IoT devices by compounding two technology approaches. It fuses multiple positioning signals like GNSS, LEO PNT & 5G and migrates the computationally intensive calculations to the Cloud or Edge. In this manner, accurate, ubiquitous, secure, and ultra-low power positioning allows the deployment of numerous IoT devices. Now this is not impossible due to power and processing resources limitations. This will be offered as Location as a Service (LaaS) framework.

Loctio business pertains to the financially prosperous low power asset tracking market that yielded 44.5B in revenues during 2019 and is projected to reach €30B by 2029. Moreover, the outlook foresees more than 550M low-power asset trackers operating in the field in the same year. Loctio is willing to make available its LaaS framework through subscriptions to Logistics, Mobility/Transportation, Surveillance, Utilities, and Insurance companies deploying millions of IoT devices that need accurate, secure, and ubiquitous outdoor and indoor positioning without sacrificing the battery longevity. Hence recurring revenues from the LaaS comprise the prime revenue stream that is anticipated to bring in tens of millions of revenues after 2024.

PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

- Cancn Cloud/Edge Location as a Service (LaaS)
- Development of GNSS and LEO PNT receivers
- Cloud/Edge based DSP processing

TECHNICAL MEANS

- Various SDR platforms for signal processing
- Power & Positioning accuracy measuring equipment

MAIN CUSTOMERS

- Cellular/mobility chipset makers
- GNSS chipset makers
- Logistics/Mobility companies
- ESA

MAJOR PROJECTS

- Embedding a GNSS receiver into an NB-IoT modem
- Implementing a LEO PNT receiver for asset tracking
- Zubeion (ESA)

UPSTREAM

MIDSTREAM

DOWNSTREAM

Satellite Navigation - IoT

CLOUD SIGNALS

CEO
Dr Christos Papachristos

FOUNDED
2020

ORGANISATION TYPE
SME

PERSONNEL
Total: 4
Space: 4

TURNOVER (2020)
Total: 88 k€
Space: 88 k€

R&D INTERNAL
INVESTMENTS (2020)
Approx. 110 k€

CORE BUSINESS

To support the broadest range of use cases, 5G needs to integrate within a comprehensive system of all available communication technologies, exploiting their particular strengths and values. Satellite networks are among the most mature communication technologies having specific advantages in geographically distributed and dynamic networks. They provide highly efficient, effective, and expedient network deployments leveraging their intrinsic advantages in broadcasting capabilities, global coverage, reduced reliance on terrestrial infrastructure and high security. Satellite networks are nowadays considered as part of the 5G use case deployments.

Many use cases can be better and more rapidly served using an integrated 5G satellite-terrestrial network rather than relying on terrestrial only solutions. These include providing communication services to remote areas and also to rural and dense urban environments like on-premises local networks, content distribution, content acquisition, highly distributed IoT networks and private mobile and nomadic network deployments.

Cloud Signals is developing a product bundle offering the transport network that connects the core network and the RAN (Radio Access Network) of the mobile network, services making use of the 5G standards and addressing 5G vertical markets (ubiquitous coverage, disaster relief, public safety requirements, emergency response, remote sensor connectivity, broadcast services, etc.) as well as corresponding use cases.

Cloud Signals was founded by executives in the Space and Telecoms industries and leverages the founders' 20+ years' experience and resources to address innovative solutions and opportunities in satellite operations, telecommunication payloads, European Space Agency and European Commission projects as well as the telecommunications markets in 4 continents.

PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

- 5G Backhaul Network as a Service (NaaS)
- Safety and Security Cloud Based Technologies
- Studies on ICT and Space selected Topics

TECHNICAL MEANS

- 5G - Satellite Demo Lab
- Sat Applications Operations Cloud

MAIN CUSTOMERS

- European Space Agency
- European Commission
- Hellenic Ministry of Digital Governance
- Hellenic Space Centre
- Space Hellas
- Satellite and ICT Operators and Service Providers
- Ground Segment Vendors

ADDRESS
Tribesinas 3,
16673 Voula, Greece

CONTACT
Dr Christos Papachristos
T: +309377889728
E: c.papachristos@cloudsignals.eu

WEB SITE
www.cloudsignals.eu

UPSTREAM

MIDSTREAM

DOWNSTREAM

Satellite Communications - 5G

Promilist

CEO
Dimitrios Farkas

FOUNDED
2022

ORGANISATION TYPE
SME

PERSONNEL
Total: 5
Space: 5

TURNOVER (2021)
Total: N/A
Space: N/A

R&D INTERNAL
INVESTMENTS (2021)
N/A

CORE BUSINESS

Our mission in Promilist is to redefine voyage optimization solutions for a sustainable maritime sector, by utilizing artificial intelligence, solid engineering models and space technology.

We have developed a state-of-the-art weather routing software that finds, in a mathematically verifiable way, the best possible route for a ship to follow with the use of artificial intelligence and graph neural networks. In this way, complicated distance calculations combined with adjustments on weather forecasts can be computed in minimal time and quite fewer resources via means of commercial GPUs.

In the shipping sector emissions have been a main issue to be addressed for maritime transportation for both economic and environmental view. Our solution reduces the fuel consumption and GHG emissions up to 20% per trip, which in turn results in savings on both fuel costs and savings from emissions taxes and penalties. In conclusion, that the maritime sector can function more efficiently while addressing climate change.

PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

- Poseidon: Weather routing optimization software accessible through an online platform
- Fuel consumption and cost calculation service (two options: integrated with Poseidon or provided separately)
- API: Readily available to other software providers with activity in the maritime sector

TECHNICAL MEANS

- Hardware accelerators
- JAX - TensorFlow Neural Networks
- Satellite Weather Data
- State-of-the-art vessel performance analysis

MAIN CUSTOMERS

- Shipping companies
- Chartering & Brokering firms
- Port States and other Marine Authorities.

MAJOR SPACE PROJECTS

Streamlined processing of the forecast products from the marine Copernicus database:

- Wave (significant height, direction, period)
- Currents (both components)
- Wind (hindcast/optional).

UPSTREAM

MIDSTREAM

DOWNSTREAM

Earth Observation - Maritime

CEO
Dr. Konstantinos Antonakopoulos

FOUNDED
2021

ORGANISATION TYPE
SME - Startup

PERSONNEL
Total: 5
Space: 5

TURNOVER (2021)
Total: N/A
Space: N/A

R&D INTERNAL INVESTMENTS (2020)
N/A

ADDRESS
Fritis Septemvriou 8,
GR-10432 Athens, Greece

CONTACT
Konstantinos Antonakopoulos
T : +30 210 44 09 899
M : +30 69 72 28 78 50
+47 93 388 66 28
E : ka@bitrezus.com

WEB SITE
www.bitrezus.com
www.astropledge.com

OTHER SITES
N/A

UPSTREAM

MIDSTREAM

DOWNSTREAM

CORE BUSINESS
Bitrezus is focusing on reducing the risk of cyberattacks against space assets, using a combination of embedded H/W and blockchain technology to create an extra level of security. Bitrezus enable critical opoce consensus in real-time, among untrusted partners, for resilient and cyber-proof operation of both space and ground infrastructure.

CORE BUSINESS
Current satellite systems were not designed with full cybersecurity in mind. They have weak encryption and use legacy systems that are not easily patched or updated. Additionally, existing cybersecurity solutions rely on terrestrial stations becoming a single point of failure and performance bottleneck and are hardly scalable due to their centralized nature. Based on reports, a cyberattack on the Global Positioning System alone could cost \$1 billion a day.

CORE BUSINESS
Our solution, Astropledge, is targeted towards the satellite manufacturing segment (upstream) and the satellite services, including ground operations. Our focus is the EU, with the European space industry being the second largest in the world, estimated to be worth €53-62 billion. Approximately 1700 satellites will be launched every year until 2030, and in the next decade we will witness a trend in the increase of mega-constellations, largely composed of small-sats, with 60% of those in the Satcom industry.

CORE BUSINESS
Our vision is to be able to evolve Astropledge to become a central component for intelligent diagnosis and self-healing of the software and firmware existing in the components and subsystems of the space asset and are vital for its operation. After 2026, our goal is to identify market opportunities in other industries internationally, such as manufacturing, maritime, energy, and others. We envisage a subscription-based model including hardware and software support and an SLA model for node maintenance, system and hardware level upgrades.

PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

- Astropledge software solution
- Astropledge embedded HW to be integrated in space objects

TECHNICAL MEANS

- Blockchain technology & governance
- Embedded HW for light-node operation
- Smart contracts

MAIN CUSTOMERS

- Satellite manufacturers (upstream) LEO, MEO, GEO
- Satellite and ICT Operators
- SMEs and Startup ecosystem
- Satellite-based Internet Services and Commercial Satellite Services Providers
- ESA, EUSPA
- Ground Segment Vendors

Satellite Software – Security

CEO
Dr. Paolo Fioravanti

FOUNDED
2018

ORGANISATION TYPE
SME

PERSONNEL
Total: 12
Space: 8

TURNOVER (2021)
Total: 280.000 €
Space: 150.000 €

R&D INTERNAL INVESTMENTS (2020)
100.000 €

ADDRESS
Kifissias Ave. 226,
GR-14562 Kifissia, Greece

CONTACT
E: info@circuitsintegrated.com
T: +30 211 18 25 891

WEB SITE
<http://circuitsintegrated.com>

OTHER SITES
N/A

UPSTREAM

MIDSTREAM

DOWNSTREAM

CORE BUSINESS
Circuits Integrated Hellas is revolutionizing the Performance and Efficiency of Phased Array Antennas with its Monolithic Microwave Integrated Circuit (MMIC). It offers a full set of "Co-design" Circuit Elements, all integrated in a unified package with autonomous operation, minimizing the need of PCBs. The revolutionary design, combined with advanced IC materials (GaAs/GaN) results in a x3 times smaller, x2 times cheaper and +20% Efficient MMIC that will empower Next Gen Phased Arrays in SATCOM. The MMIC market for the SATCOM is currently ~2bn Euros and is expected to be doubled in the next decade. Additional similar use-cases such as 5G, defence in-circue potentially to 5bn Euros. CI aspires to become a leading chip consultant, design house and supplier in GaN/GaAs based designs for the SATCOM industry.

PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

- Development of Proprietary IP (Consultation/Design) Chip Design – 3D IC MMIC - GaAs/GaN
- MMIC Transceivers for SATCOM Industry Proprietary IP (Consultation/Design/Fabrication)

TECHNICAL MEANS

- Various EDAs Cadence, Keysight, 3D EM
- Data Processing Octave
- Computational Power High Performance 128 cores/Linux Based Privately Owned Servers, Optimized for Computational Analysis on RFIC and MMIC Design and Simulation

MAIN CUSTOMERS

- ESA
- Phased Array Antenna Companies
- RF & MMIC Chipset Manufacturers
- SATCOM chipset providers

MAJOR PROJECTS

- MMIC for the SATCOM industry (K band), Product and IP
- "3D TOPOS", R&D on 3D Integrated Circuit Design on GaN and Si
- High Speed Chip Design for Optoelectronic Application (Data Communication)

Satellite Hardware – Antennas

CEO
Antonios Gotsis

FOUNDED
2021

ORGANISATION TYPE
SME

PERSONNEL
Total: 3

TURNOVER (2021)
Total: € 20,000

R&D INTERNAL INVESTMENTS (2021)
€ 100,000

ADDRESS
30 Arachovis Street
GR-10681 Athens
Greece

CONTACT
Antonios Gotsis
T: +30 210503386
E: anto-
nis.gotsis@insigh.io

WEB SITE
www.insigh.io

UPSTREAM

MIDSTREAM

DOWNSTREAM

CORE BUSINESS
At INSIGHIO we accelerate IoT adoption, from conception to final product, with a unique application-agnostic hardware and software technology stack. We help third parties to overcome the technological entry barriers which prevail today and are slowing down the IoT uptake. Relying on an in-house developed technology and a fast-track IoT applications design and implementation service, we solve one of the biggest challenges in today's new IoT projects: the inadequate Proof-of-Concept during early stages. Thanks to a flexible and modular hardware backed by a fully customizable firmware and Cloud software, INSIGHIO bridges the gap between prototyping and production, scaling an IoT deployment from a few nodes to hundreds of nodes, in a very short time frame.

CORE BUSINESS
With only 10-15% of the Earth's surface having access to terrestrial connectivity, the Satellite IoT industry is responding with a variety of low cost, low power direct-to-satellite network services. INSIGHIO steps into this multi-billion and fast-growing market, enabling rapid design, testing, and upscaling of novel IoT applications harnessing terrestrial and new satellite IoT connectivity technologies. This offering extends to countless domains, including precision agriculture, environmental monitoring, asset tracking, and alerting in remote oil, gas, and construction industries.

PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

- insigh.io Node:** A generic IoT hardware device embedding multiple technologies (including Satellite IoT Connectivity ones) used as a development board or in end applications
- insigh.io Platform:** An end-to-end IoT software suite with many integrations taking care of all end-point and cloud functionalities
- insigh.io Service:** A bundle of rapid IoT application design, prototyping and deployment, built on-top of the insigh.io stack

TECHNICAL MEANS

- 100% in-house hardware design** encompassing a programmable micro-controller, low-energy consumption, various energy sources with automatic power management, flexible short and long range connectivity, and inherent support for attaching numerous external sensors
- Open-source firmware** and a flexible **back-end/front-end** offering advanced device management - with remote update capabilities- along with data provision, analysis, and visualization

MAIN CUSTOMERS

- Integrators & Solution providers who look for the core IoT building blocks
- Businesses in the need of IoT hardware/software to automate processes
- R&D groups requiring the proper IoT enablers to back their research work
- Any company/organization wanting to test a new IoT idea

Satellite Communications- IoT

FIND US

Phone: +30 210 6300770

Email: info@esa-bic.gr

Web: www.esa-bic.gr

Facebook: [esabiggreece](https://www.facebook.com/esabiggreece)

Instagram: [esabiggreece](https://www.instagram.com/esabiggreece)

Twitter: [esabiggreece](https://twitter.com/esabiggreece)

LinkedIn: [esa-bic-greece](https://www.linkedin.com/company/esa-bic-greece)